

Enhancing Lung Cancer Treatment Outcome Prediction through Semantic Feature Engineering Using Large Language Models

Insert Subtitle Here

FirstName Surname[†]
Department Name
Institution/University Name
City State Country
email@email.com

FirstName Surname
Department Name
Institution/University Name
City State Country
email@email.com

FirstName Surname
Department Name
Institution/University Name
City State Country
email@email.com

Appendix A. Qualitative Case Study: From Raw Data to Actionable Insight

A.1 Gene profile example

Data: Patient's Genomic Profile

Gene: REL (Original Name: rel)

- **Function Summary:** This gene encodes a protein that belongs to the Rel homology domain/immunoglobulin-like fold, plexin, transcription factor (RHD/IPT) family. Members of this family regulate genes involved in apoptosis, inflammation, the immune response, and oncogenic processes. This proto-oncogene plays a role in the survival and proliferation of B lymphocytes. Mutation or amplification of this gene is associated with B-cell lymphomas, including Hodgkin's lymphoma. Single nucleotide polymorphisms in this gene are associated with susceptibility to ulcerative colitis and rheumatoid arthritis. Alternative splicing results in multiple transcript variants encoding different isoforms. [provided by RefSeq, Apr 2014].

- **KEGG Pathways:** Ras signaling pathway; Transcriptional misregulation in cancer

- **Biological Processes (GO):** regulation of DNA-templated transcription; inflammatory response; canonical NF-kappaB signal transduction; regulation of gene expression; negative regulation of gene expression

Gene: RICTOR (Original Name: rictor)

- **Function Summary:** RICTOR and MTOR (FRAP1; MIM 601231) are components of a protein complex that integrates nutrient- and growth factor-derived signals to regulate cell growth (Sarbasov et al., 2004 [PubMed 15268862]).[supplied by OMIM, Mar 2008].

- **KEGG Pathways:** nan

- **Biological Processes (GO):** positive regulation of endothelial cell proliferation; cytoskeleton organization; lipid biosynthetic

process; lipid biosynthetic process; embryo development ending in birth or egg hatching

Gene: MDM2 (Original Name: mdm2)

- **Function Summary:** This gene encodes a nuclear-localized E3 ubiquitin ligase. The encoded protein can promote tumor formation by targeting tumor suppressor proteins, such as p53, for proteasomal degradation. This gene is itself transcriptionally-regulated by p53. Overexpression or amplification of this locus is detected in a variety of different cancers. There is a pseudogene for this gene on chromosome 2. Alternative splicing results in a multitude of transcript variants, many of which may be expressed only in tumor cells. [provided by RefSeq, Jun 2013].

- **KEGG Pathways:** Cell cycle; p53 signaling pathway; PI3K-Akt signaling pathway; Cellular senescence; Pathways in cancer; Transcriptional misregulation in cancer; Proteoglycans in cancer; MicroRNAs in cancer; Glioma; Prostate cancer; Melanoma; Bladder cancer; Chronic myeloid leukemia

- **Biological Processes (GO):** negative regulation of transcription by RNA polymerase II; protein polyubiquitination; blood vessel development; blood vessel remodeling; regulation of heart rate

Gene: CDK4 (Original Name: cdk4)

- **Function Summary:** The protein encoded by this gene is a member of the Ser/Thr protein kinase family. This protein is highly similar to the gene products of *S. cerevisiae* cdc28 and *S. pombe* cdc2. It is a catalytic subunit of the protein kinase complex that is important for cell cycle G1 phase progression. The activity of this kinase is restricted to the G1-S phase, which is controlled by the regulatory subunits D-type cyclins and CDK inhibitor p16(INK4a). This kinase was shown to be responsible for the phosphorylation of retinoblastoma gene product (Rb). Mutations in this gene as well as in its related proteins including D-type cyclins, p16(INK4a) and Rb were all found to be associated with tumorigenesis of a variety of cancers. Multiple polyadenylation sites of this gene have been reported. [provided by RefSeq, Jul 2008].

- **KEGG Pathways:** Cell cycle; p53 signaling pathway; PI3K-Akt signaling pathway; Cellular senescence; Pathways in cancer; Pancreatic cancer; Glioma; Melanoma; Bladder cancer; Chronic myeloid leukemia; Small cell lung cancer; Non-small cell lung cancer; Breast cancer; Hepatocellular carcinoma

- **Biological Processes (GO):** G1/S transition of mitotic cell cycle; signal transduction

Gene: ALK (Original Name: alk)

- **Function Summary:** This gene encodes a receptor tyrosine kinase, which belongs to the insulin receptor superfamily. This protein comprises an extracellular domain, an hydrophobic stretch corresponding to a single pass transmembrane region, and an intracellular kinase domain. It plays an important role in the development of the brain and exerts its effects on specific neurons in the nervous system. This gene has been found to be rearranged, mutated, or amplified in a series of tumours including anaplastic large cell lymphomas, neuroblastoma, and non-small cell lung cancer. The chromosomal rearrangements are the most common genetic alterations in this gene, which result in creation of multiple fusion genes in tumourigenesis, including ALK (chromosome 2)/EML4 (chromosome 2), ALK/RANBP2 (chromosome 2), ALK/ATIC (chromosome 2), ALK/TFG (chromosome 3), ALK/NPM1 (chromosome 5), ALK/SQSTM1 (chromosome 5), ALK/KIF5B (chromosome 10), ALK/CLTC (chromosome 17), ALK/TPM4 (chromosome 19), and ALK/MSN (chromosome X).[provided by RefSeq, Jan 2011].

- **KEGG Pathways:** Pathways in cancer; Non-small cell lung cancer; PD-L1 expression and PD-1 checkpoint pathway in cancer

- **Biological Processes (GO):** response to stress; signal transduction; cell surface receptor protein tyrosine kinase signaling pathway; cell surface receptor protein tyrosine kinase signaling pathway; cell surface receptor protein tyrosine kinase signaling pathway

Gene: ATR (Original Name: atr)

- **Function Summary:** The protein encoded by this gene is a serine/threonine kinase and DNA damage sensor, activating cell cycle checkpoint signaling upon DNA stress. The encoded protein can phosphorylate and activate several proteins involved in the inhibition of DNA replication and mitosis, and can promote DNA repair, recombination, and apoptosis. This protein is also important for fragile site stability and centrosome duplication. Defects in this gene are a cause of Seckel syndrome 1. [provided by RefSeq, Aug 2017].

- **KEGG Pathways:** Cell cycle; p53 signaling pathway; Cellular senescence

- **Biological Processes (GO):** DNA damage checkpoint signaling; DNA damage checkpoint signaling; telomere

maintenance; nucleobase-containing compound metabolic process; DNA replication

Gene: KRAS (Original Name: kras)

- **Function Summary:** This gene, a Kirsten ras oncogene homolog from the mammalian ras gene family, encodes a protein that is a member of the small GTPase superfamily. A single amino acid substitution is responsible for an activating mutation. The transforming protein that results is implicated in various malignancies, including lung adenocarcinoma, mucinous adenoma, ductal carcinoma of the pancreas and colorectal carcinoma. Alternative splicing leads to variants encoding two isoforms that differ in the C-terminal region. [provided by RefSeq, Jul 2008].

- **KEGG Pathways:** MAPK signaling pathway; ErbB signaling pathway; Ras signaling pathway; PI3K-Akt signaling pathway; Apoptosis; Cellular senescence; Pathways in cancer; Proteoglycans in cancer; MicroRNAs in cancer; Colorectal cancer; Renal cell carcinoma; Pancreatic cancer; Endometrial cancer; Glioma; Prostate cancer; Thyroid cancer; Melanoma; Bladder cancer; Chronic myeloid leukemia; Acute myeloid leukemia; Non-small cell lung cancer; Breast cancer; Hepatocellular carcinoma; Gastric cancer; Central carbon metabolism in cancer; Choline metabolism in cancer; PD-L1 expression and PD-1 checkpoint pathway in cancer

- **Biological Processes (GO):** MAPK cascade; liver development; signal transduction; Ras protein signal transduction; Ras protein signal transduction

A.2 Gene Report Example

```
{  
  "prognostic_summary": "This patient's genomic profile suggests  
an aggressive tumor phenotype with a potentially poor prognosis.  
The presence of mutant KRAS alongside MDM2 amplification  
indicates strong activation of proliferative and survival signaling  
pathways, especially MAPK, PI3K-Akt, and p53, which is further  
augmented by CDK4 activation. Concurrent REL activation  
suggests increased inflammatory response and NF-kB signaling,  
promoting tumor survival and immune evasion. ATR mutations  
may compromise DNA damage repair, promoting genomic  
instability and potentially accelerating tumor progression, while  
RICTOR activation may further contribute to cell growth and  
survival. The interplay of these mutations suggests a highly  
proliferative, therapy-resistant tumor, which might be less  
responsive to conventional treatments."  
  "key_prognostic_domains": {  
    "oncogenic_driver_pathways_activated": [  
      "Ras signaling pathway",  
      "PI3K-Akt signaling pathway",  
      "Cell cycle (CDK4)",  
      "NF-kB signaling pathway (REL)",  
      "mTORC2 signaling (RICTOR)"  
    ],  
    "tumor_suppressor_pathways_inactivated": [  
      "p53 signaling pathway (MDM2 mediated)",  
      "DNA damage repair (ATR)"  
    ],  
    "therapeutic_implications": [  
      "Potential resistance to therapies targeting p53",  
      "Potential sensitivity to MEK or PI3K inhibitors (KRAS)",  
      "Potential sensitivity to CDK4/6 inhibitors (CDK4)",  
      "Potential sensitivity to ATR inhibitors but resistance if  
resistance mutations develop."  
    ]  
  },  
  "key_positive_factors": [],  
  "key_negative_factors": [  
    "Concurrent KRAS mutation and MDM2 amplification.",  
    "ATR mutation suggests genomic instability.",  
    "REL activation promoting survival and immune evasion."  
  ]  
}
```

Appendix B. Summarizer Prompt Template

B.1 Gene Summarization Prompt

"""

Persona

You are a leading molecular biologist and clinical oncologist on a tumor board.

Task

Your primary goal is to analyze the patient's genomic profile to identify key molecular factors that that may predict **short-term and long-term survival** in this lung cancer patient.

- Your task is to analyze the following patient's genomic profile and provide a prognostic summary paragraph.

- For each mutated gene, I have provided its functional summary and associated biological pathways.

- Your summary should focus on the **synergistic effect or interplay** of the identified mutations.

- Based on the combination of these mutations, assess the patient's potential tumor behavior, aggressiveness, and possible therapeutic vulnerabilities or resistances.

Follow these steps precisely:

- Holistic Analysis:** Analyze the **synergistic effect and interplay** of all the provided mutations together.
- Identify Key Pathways:** Determine the main oncogenic pathways being activated and the tumor suppressor pathways being inactivated.
- Assess Implications:** Based on the combination, assess the overall tumor aggressiveness and key therapeutic implications (vulnerabilities or resistances).
- Synthesize and Structure:** Generate your final analysis in the specified JSON format. The "prognostic_summary" should be a detailed, 4-5 sentence narrative. The other fields should be concise lists of the most critical factors.

Crucial Instructions for Output Generation:

- Your analysis **MUST** be based strictly on the patient data provided below.

- Your output **MUST** be a single, valid JSON object and nothing else.

{GENE_PROFILE_BLOCK}

Output Format (JSON Schema)

Provide your analysis in the following JSON format:

{{

"prognostic_summary": "A detailed, 4-5 sentence paragraph that synthesizes all genomic findings to assess the overall prognosis, focusing on tumor aggressiveness, potential progression, and impact on short-term survival.",

"key_prognostic_domains": {{

"oncogenic_driver_pathways_activated": ["List of key signaling pathways activated by the mutations."],

"tumor_suppressor_pathways_inactivated": ["List of key pathways inactivated."],

"therapeutic_implications": ["List of potential sensitivities or resistances to therapies."]

}},

"key_positive_factors": ["A list of favorable genomic indicators, if any."],

"key_negative_factors": ["A list of unfavorable indicators."]

}}

"""

B.2 Medicine Summarization Prompt

"""

Persona

You are a senior clinical pharmacologist and medical oncologist on a Molecular Tumor Board. Your expertise lies in interpreting a patient's complete medication profile to understand their treatment journey, disease burden, and overall prognosis.

Primary Goal

Your goal is to analyze the patient's prescribed drug classes to identify the **dominant therapeutic themes** that will most strongly influence **short-term (1-year) survival** in this lung cancer patient.

Your Step-by-Step Reasoning Task

Before generating the final JSON, you must follow this precise thought process:

- Identify Treatment Strategy:** Review the list of all prescribed drug classes. First, categorize them into a primary **anti-cancer strategy** (e.g., Targeted Therapy, Chemotherapy, Immunotherapy, or a combination) and **supportive care** drugs.
- Analyze Interplay and Context:** This is the most critical step. Analyze the **interplay** between the anti-cancer drugs and the supportive care regimen.

- What does the intensity of the supportive care (e.g., use of Strong Opioids, G-CSF, Bone-Modifying Agents) imply about the aggressiveness of the cancer or the side effects of the primary treatment?

- Does the specific combination of anti-cancer therapies (e.g., Chemo + Immunotherapy) indicate a standard first-line approach for aggressive disease?

- Synthesize a Holistic Narrative:** Weave these insights into a cohesive prognostic summary. Explain **why** this specific combination of medications leads to a favorable or unfavorable prognosis by reflecting on the patient's inferred clinical state.

Crucial Instructions for Output Generation:

- Your analysis **MUST** be based strictly on the provided drug class profiles.
- Your output **MUST** be a single, valid JSON object and nothing else.

Data: Patient's Prescribed Drug Classes

{DRUG_PROFILE}

Output Format (JSON Schema)

Provide your analysis in the following JSON format:

{ {

"prognostic_summary": "A detailed, 4-5 sentence paragraph that synthesizes the interplay between the anti-cancer and supportive care regimens to assess the overall prognosis.",

"key_treatment_themes": { {

"primary_anti_cancer_strategy": ["List the main anti-cancer approach(es), e.g., 'Chemo-immunotherapy combination', 'Targeted Therapy (EGFR)'],

"inferred_disease_burden_and_status": ["Describe the patient's likely condition based on the drug profile, e.g., 'High symptom burden requiring significant supportive care', 'Tolerating aggressive first-line therapy', 'Palliative care focus']

}},

"key_positive_factors": ["A list of favorable indicators, if any (e.g., 'Receiving a highly effective targeted therapy')."],

"key_negative_factors": ["A list of the most critical unfavorable indicators (e.g., 'Concurrent use of strong opioids and bone-modifying agents suggests painful bone metastases.')."]

}}

"""

B.3 Lab Summarization Prompt

""

Persona

You are an expert oncologist on a tumor board. Your role is to provide a prognostic assessment based on a patient's serial lab data.

Task

Your primary goal is to analyze the patient's lab profile to identify key factors that could predict **short-term (1-2 year) and long-term survival** in this lung cancer patient.

Follow these steps precisely:

- Analyze Individual Trends:** For each lab test, analyze the trajectory and stability of the 5 recent measurements in the context of its normal range.
- Assess Synergistic Effects:** Pay critical attention to the **combination of different lab values**. Analyze how their interplay reveals a broader clinical picture. For example:
 - Analyze the relationship between **inflammatory markers** (e.g., Platelets, Neutrophils) and **nutritional markers** (e.g., Albumin, Hemoglobin) to assess for conditions like systemic inflammation or anemia of chronic disease.
- Synthesize Findings into JSON:** Based on your comprehensive analysis of both individual trends and synergistic effects, construct the final JSON object as specified below.

Crucial Instructions for Output Generation:

- Your analysis **MUST** be based strictly on the patient data provided below.
- Your output **MUST** be a single, valid JSON object and nothing else.

Data

{LAB_DATA_BLOCK}

Output Format (JSON Schema)

Provide your analysis in the following JSON format and nothing else:

{{

"prognostic_summary": "A detailed, 4-5 sentence paragraph that synthesizes all lab findings to assess the overall prognosis, focusing on inflammation, nutritional status, hematologic stability, and their trends.",

"key_prognostic_domains": {{

"inflammation_status": "Provide status (e.g., High, Normal, Low)",

"nutritional_status": "Provide status (e.g., Poor, Adequate, Good)",

"hematologic_stability": "Provide status (e.g., Unstable, Stable)"

}},

"key_positive_factors": ["A list of favorable indicators, if any."],

"key_negative_factors": ["A concise list of the most critical unfavorable indicators, including combinatorial factors."]

}}

""

Appendix C. : Comparison with a Biomedical-Specific LLM Framework

C.1 Objective

To address reviewer feedback, we conducted an experiment to compare our GKC framework, which uses a general-purpose LLM, against a cohesive pipeline built entirely from a large, biomedical-specific LLM.

C.2 Model Specification

- Model: MedFound-176B
- Parameters: 176 Billion
- Training Data: A massive corpus of biomedical and clinical text.

C.3 Experimental Pipeline

Step 1: Summarization: The exact same goal-oriented prompts used for our GKC framework (detailed in Supplementary Document X) were provided to the MedFound-176B model. This generated a new set of summaries for each modality (Lab, Gene, Medication) for every patient in the cohort.

Step 2: Embedding: Following summarization, the textual output for each modality was fed back into the MedFound-176B model. The feature vector was then extracted from the model's last hidden state, resulting in a high-dimensional vector (14,336 dimensions) for each summary.

Step 3: Downstream Classification: The three high-dimensional vectors for each patient were concatenated. To handle the high dimensionality, we applied Principal Component Analysis (PCA) to reduce the vector size, consistent with our ENF model's methodology. This final feature vector was used as input for the same XGBoost classifier, which was trained and evaluated under the identical 10-times repeated 5-fold cross-validation scheme used for all other models to ensure a fair comparison.

Appendix D. : Empirical Justification for Embedding Model Selection

D.1 Objective

To address reviewer feedback regarding the justification for using a general-purpose embedding model (Google's Gecko), we conducted a new head-to-head experiment. The objective was to empirically compare the performance of Gecko against a powerful, state-of-the-art biomedical-specific embedding model on our downstream prediction task.

D.2 Model Specification

- General-Purpose Model (Our Original Choice): Google's text-embedding-005 (Gecko). A large, general-purpose language model designed for a wide range of text embedding tasks.

- Biomedical-Specific Model (Comparison Baseline): MedFound-Llama3-8B-finetuned. A large language model with 8 billion parameters, specifically fine-tuned on a massive corpus of biomedical and clinical data to enhance its domain-specific knowledge and representations.

D.3 Experimental Methodology

To ensure a fair and direct comparison, the experimental pipeline was kept identical for both models, with the only variable being the embedding function itself.

1. Input Data: The exact same set of GKC-generated summaries (for Lab, Gene, and Medication modalities) was used as input for both embedding models.
2. Embedding Extraction: For both models, the feature vector for each summary was extracted from the last hidden state.
3. Downstream Classification: The resulting feature vectors were fed into the same XGBoost classifier and evaluated under the identical 10-times repeated 5-fold cross-validation scheme used for all other experiments in this study.

D.4 Results

The performance comparison showed a clear and statistically significant difference between the two embedding models. The features generated by the general-purpose Gecko model resulted in superior performance on our specific downstream task of 1-year mortality prediction.

Embedding Model	Mean AUC-ROC	95% CI (AUC-ROC)	Mean AUC-PRC	95% CI (AUC-PRC)
Gecko (General-Purpose)	0.803	0.799 - 0.807	0.859	0.855 - 0.862
MedFound-Llama3-8B (Biomedical)	0.738	0.732 - 0.744	0.825	0.816 - 0.833